

Patient Preparation:

- Patient fasted for 4 to 6 hours.
- The bladder was moderately filled.
- A phased-array surface coil was placed over the pelvis.
- It was not possible to administer an antispasmodic agent to reduce motion artifacts caused by intestinal peristalsis.

Examination Procedure: Protocol and Sequence Parameters:

The pelvic MRI examinations for the characterization of an adnexal mass were performed according to a standardized protocol.

1. **2D Fast Spin Echo T2 sequence centered on the pelvis in the sagittal, axial, and coronal planes.**

Slice Thickness	Spacing	Repetition Time (TR)	Echo Time (TE)	Field of View (FOV)	Matrix	Number of Excitations (NEX)
4 mm	0.5 mm	5523 ms	114 ms	26 cm	320 (Propeller)	2

2. **T2* lymph node sequence (Fast Spin Echo) SSFSE in a strict axial plane, from the renal hila to the pubic symphysis.**

Slice Thickness	Spacing	TR	TE	FOV
5 mm	0 mm	1000 ms	90 ms	38 cm

3. **Diffusion sequence with ADC mapping in an axial plane.**

Two B-values (50 and 800) as well as a synthetic diffusion (1000, 1200, and 14000) were used.

Slice Thickness	Spacing	TR	TE	FOV
4 mm	1 mm	5188 ms	70 ms	38 cm

4. **3D LAVA FLEX T1 Gradient Echo sequence in a strict axial plane.**

Slice Thickness	Spacing	TR	TE1-TE2	FOV	Matrix	Number of Excitations (NEX)
2 mm	-	6.3	2.1 - 4.2	32 cm	320 x 320	1

5. Dynamic acquisition in a strict axial plane with a T1 DISCO Gradient Echo sequence after manual intravenous injection of a simple dose of Gadolinium (Dotarem©), 0.1 ml/kg at a flow rate of 2 ml/sec.

The time separation between the non-injected sequence and the 1st injected sequence was 11 seconds. The dynamic study includes four sequential acquisitions, with a 60-second interval between each and acquisition times ranging from 9 to 11 seconds. The first sequence starts immediately after the intravenous contrast injection. Thus, an average of 20 acquisitions are obtained.

Time resolution	Slice thickness	TR	TE1-TE2	FOV	Matrix	Number of Excitations (NEX)
9.5 sec	4 mm	6.6	2.1 - 4.3	32 cm	320 x 320	1

6. 3D LAVA FLEX T1 GADO 5min Gradient Echo sequence in a strict axial plane.

Slice Thickness	Spacing	TR	TE1-TE2	FOV	Matrix	Number of Excitations (NEX)
2 mm	-	6.3	2.1 - 4.2	32 cm	320 x 320	1